

CLINICAL COURSE AND DIAGNOSIS OF OMPHALOCELE - GASTROSCHISIS IN NEWBORNS

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ABSTRACT

In 2006-2022, a total of 243 children with various defects of the anterior abdominal wall were examined and treated at the Republican Educational, Treatment and Methodological Center for Neonatal Surgery at the Republican Perinatal Center. Of these, 140 (57.6%) were boys, 103 (42.4%) were girls. The children were 0-4 days old. Congenital defects of the anterior abdominal wall in children were omphalocele - 133 (53.9%) and gastroschisis - 110 (44.5%). Of the 110 (45.3%) children born with gastroschisis, 62 (56.4%) were boys and 48 (43.6%) were girls. Of the 133 (54.7%) children born with omphalocele, 78 (58.6%) were boys and 55 (41.4%) were girls. Of the 243 infants, 165 (67.9%) were born full-term, and 78 (32.1%) were premature

Introduction. To analyze the clinical course and diagnosis of congenital defects of the anterior abdominal wall in newborns.

Material and methods. In 2006-2022, a total of 243 children with various defects of the anterior abdominal wall were examined and treated at the Republican Educational, Treatment and Methodological Center for Neonatal Surgery at the Republican Perinatal Center. Of these, 140 (57.6%) were boys, 103 (42.4%) were girls. The children were 0-4 days old. Congenital defects of the anterior abdominal wall in children were omphalocele - 133 (53.9%) and gastroschisis - 110 (44.5%). Of the 110 (45.3%) children born with gastroschisis, 62 (56.4%) were boys and 48 (43.6%) were girls. Of the 133 (54.7%) children born with omphalocele, 78 (58.6%) were boys and 55 (41.4%) were girls. Of the 243 infants, 165 (67.9%) were born full-term, and 78 (32.1%) were premature. Complications during the course of the disease and treatment were observed primarily in premature infants. Complications were observed in 102 (46.2%) of the 221 children who underwent surgery. Of these, 69 (67.6%) were born premature. Upon presentation to the clinic, in addition to general clinical examination, all patients underwent general abdominal radiography, ultrasound examination of the internal organs and the anterior abdominal wall defect, echocardiography, and neurosonography.

Results and discussion. Gastroschisis and omphalocele are the most common congenital defects of the anterior abdominal wall in young children. Their clinical course is primarily determined by cardiovascular and respiratory system activity, as well as abdominal organ function, which influences treatment outcomes. Based on the above, we studied the clinical course of gastroschisis and omphalocele in young children, dividing them into

uncomplicated and complicated forms. The clinical course of gastroschisis and omphalocele was influenced by tachycardia, cyanosis, tachypnea, oliguria, hepatomegaly, and hypothermia. In gastroschisis, the umbilical ring and umbilical system are preserved, and the abdominal organs are located externally through a defect in the anterior abdominal wall to the right of the umbilicus. Thirty-one patients (28.2%) showed signs of severe inflammation in the internal organs located outside the abdominal cavity, including extremely small, underdeveloped internal organs, a very thick mesentery characteristic only of the small and large intestines, and a fibrinous coating on the pale pink and bluish intestinal surface. Twenty-three patients (20.9%) with a small abdominal wall defect due to intestinal and mesenteric compression showed symptoms of venous and vascular dampness and lymphostasis. The above clinical signs were detected separately or together in each case and led to positive or negative treatment outcomes.

In recent years, the use of modern examination methods in medicine has increased the possibility of detecting congenital defects of the anterior abdominal wall in the antenatal period. The main goal of antenatal diagnosis is to determine the method of pregnancy management and plan a delivery program in specialized centers and perinatal centers with a neonatal surgery department. Due to the widespread use of ultrasound in obstetrics, omphalocele and gastroschisis are often detected during pregnancy rather than during postnatal examination. At 10 weeks of gestation, ultrasound reveals a physiological fetal hernia in the abdominal cavity, which should resolve within the abdominal cavity by 13 weeks of gestation. At 13 weeks of gestation, the appearance of intestinal loops without return into the abdominal cavity indicates the development of omphalocele and gastroschisis. For this reason, antenatal diagnosis of gastroschisis and omphalocele is performed after 13 weeks, using ultrasound and Doppler ultrasound.

Conclusion: Thus, the clinical course of children born with a congenital anterior abdominal wall defect depended on the child's characteristics, medical history, type and severity of the defect, and gestational age. Antenatal diagnosis after the 13th week of pregnancy is advisable and helps determine positive treatment outcomes..

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